

Bacteriological Quality and Proximate Analysis of Garri Sold in Ika Locality, Delta State Nigeria

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Abstract:

Background: Garri, a widely consumed staple food made from cassava (*Manihot esculenta*) is commonly sold in open-air markets, which may expose it to microbial contamination due to improper handling and storage. This study investigates the microbiological safety, proximate composition, and functional properties of garri sold in various open markets in Ika locality, Delta State, Nigeria. **Method:** A total of ten garri samples, both yellow and white, were randomly collected from five markets. Standard methods were used to perform bacteriological analyses. Proximate analysis was performed to determine the moisture content, swelling capacity, and functional properties of garri samples. Moisture content was determined using the oven-drying method. Swelling capacity was assessed by measuring the volume change when garri was mixed with distilled water. **Results:** Proximate analysis revealed that the moisture content of the samples ranged from 5.50% to 9.00%, with higher moisture content being associated with increased microbial growth. The microbiological analysis indicated bacterial contamination ranging from 1.42×10^3 CFU/g to 7.1×10^5 CFU/g, surpassing the acceptable limits for ready-to-eat foods. Pathogenic bacteria such as *Escherichia coli* and *Staphylococcus aureus* were identified, posing significant public health risks. Additionally, functional properties, including swelling capacity, varied between 3.00% and 3.60%, indicating differences in the cassava varieties used and fermentation processes. **Conclusion:** The findings highlight the significant health risks associated with garri consumption, particularly due to poor hygiene practices during production and handling. Recommendations include improving drying techniques, educating vendors on food safety, and conducting routine market surveillance. Future research should focus on the antibiotic resistance profiles of the bacterial isolates and investigate the presence of mycotoxins in garri. This study underscores the importance of ensuring food safety in garri production to mitigate health risks for consumers.

Keywords: garri, microbiological safety, proximate analysis, bacterial contamination, public health, food safety, Nigeria.

Introduction

Garri, a widely consumed food product in West Africa, particularly Nigeria, is produced from the roots of *Manihot esculenta* (cassava). This granular, hygroscopic product is essential to food security in the region, offering an affordable and accessible source of carbohydrates for both rural and urban populations. Nigeria, being one of the largest producers of cassava in the world, cultivates approximately 10 million tons annually (Ikueomonisan et al., 2020). The role of garri in addressing food insecurity in Nigeria and the broader West African region cannot be overstated, as it plays a significant part in ensuring nutritional balance despite socio-economic challenges. Garri is produced by a series of steps, including the harvesting, peeling, grating, fermentation, and frying of cassava tubers. The final product can either be yellow or white, depending on whether palm oil is added during the frying process. The white garri retains its creamy color, while the yellow variety adopts a characteristic hue from the addition of palm oil (Thomas et al., 2021).

While garri provides an affordable source of calories, it has a relatively low nutritional profile. The proximate analysis of garri typically reveals a high carbohydrate content, but low levels of protein, fat, and micronutrients (Bamidele et al., 2014; Farinde et al., 2023). Its primary role in the diet is to serve as a source of energy, but its limited nutritional content underscores the need for complementary food sources to ensure balanced nutrition, especially in areas with limited access to other sources of protein and vitamins. Furthermore, garri's high carbohydrate content makes it a vital energy source for a majority of the population, particularly in the context of food insecurity in rural Nigeria. The cassava plantation of Ika locality in Delta State, Nigeria is called 'Ekwu-Garri' or 'Ali-garri' in the Ika dialect. Cassava, the raw material used in garri production, contains both macro- and micronutrients. The macro-components mainly consist of carbohydrates, specifically starch, which provides a high-energy yield. Cassava also contains small amounts of protein and fats, while its micronutrient content includes vitamins like vitamin C and B vitamins, as well as minerals such as calcium, iron, and zinc. However, cassava also contains cyanogenic glycosides, specifically linamarin and lotaustralin, which can release cyanide when improperly processed (Ogiehor et al., 2007). Cyanide is a potent toxin, and if not effectively removed during the processing of cassava, it can present significant health risks to consumers (Ferreira et al., 2021). Therefore, proper processing methods, including fermentation and adequate drying, are essential to reduce the cyanide content and ensure the safety of garri.

The safety of garri is a significant concern due to its vulnerability to microbial contamination, which can pose health risks when consumed, particularly in situations where it is not subjected to further cooking. The contamination of garri can occur at various stages of its

production and handling, including during the processing of cassava tubers, the fermentation stage, and during the display and sale of the final product. Garri is often sold in open-air markets where it is exposed to dust, dirt, and microbial contamination from environmental sources, including vehicle exhaust and airborne pathogens (Egbuobi et al., 2015; Sorkheh et al., 2022). Studies have shown that pathogens such as *Salmonella sp.*, *Escherichia coli*, and *Aspergillus* species are frequently isolated from garri samples, making it crucial to address these contamination concerns in order to safeguard public health (Koledoye et al., 2012).

In addition to cyanogenic glycosides, the microbial contamination of garri is another critical concern. During the processing and handling of cassava, a wide variety of microorganisms, including bacteria, fungi, and molds, can contaminate the product. The fermentation process, while important for detoxifying the cassava and enhancing its nutritional profile, can also provide an environment conducive to the growth of harmful microorganisms if not properly controlled (Thomas et al., 2021). Microorganisms such as *Escherichia coli*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, and various species of *Aspergillus* have been found in garri sold in markets, raising concerns about its safety for consumption. These pathogens, especially *Escherichia coli* are indicators of fecal contamination and can lead to gastrointestinal diseases and other foodborne infections (Okolo & Makanjuola, 2021; Thomas et al., 2021).

The microbiological safety of garri is further compromised by the conditions in which it is sold. Most garri sold in Nigerian markets is displayed in open bowls or bags, exposed to environmental contaminants such as dust, insects, and vehicle emissions. The frequent exposure to airborne microorganisms, combined with the unhygienic handling practices by vendors and consumers, further exacerbates the potential for contamination. Moreover, consumers often test garri by touching it with their hands, which introduces additional pathogens, thus contributing to the overall microbiological load of the product. In the absence of further thermal treatment, such as boiling or frying before consumption, the risk of foodborne illness is heightened, especially for vulnerable populations like children, the elderly, and immunocompromised individuals (Okolo & Makanjuola, 2021).

While garri remains a critical component of the Nigerian diet, its safety and nutritional quality are compromised by inadequate processing practices, poor hygiene, and improper storage conditions. Addressing these issues requires a multifaceted approach, involving improvements in production methods, better hygiene practices among vendors, and public health interventions aimed at educating consumers about the risks of consuming garri without thermal treatment (Feng et al., 2023).

The current study aim is to assess the bacteriological quality and proximate composition of garri sold in Ika Locality, Delta State, Nigeria. To isolate and identify bacterial contaminants present in garri samples from different markets in Ika Locality and evaluate the potential health risk.

Materials and Methods

Study Area

This study was carried out in Ika locality, the Ika south and the Ika Northeast local government area of Delta State Nigeria. Geographically, it is located within latitude 6° 16' 0'' N and longitude 6° 9', 0'' E at an altitude of 130 meters. The samples collected were bought from five (5) various markets in regions of the locality. The samples collected were bought and labelled according to the town and market of purchase. The samples (yellow garri and white garri) purchased from Owa market and Ebu-Owa market was labelled sample C1, C2, D1, and D2 respectively. Ika south locality, from Agbor-Obi, Balake market, and Alihagu market were the samples yellow and white garri labelled, A1, A2, B1, B2, E1, and E2 respectively.

The primary sampling site was the markets in Ika locality, Delta State Nigeria. These markets are open to everyone students, workers and travellers wanting to buy either goods or products. During sales and transaction, testing and feeling of products like garri, makes it a potential point for microbial contamination due to frequent hand contact and inadequate drying or unhygienic practices by the costumers or handlers.

Sample Collection

Ten (10) samples were purchased randomly two (2) each from five (5) various markets in regions of Ika locality. The samples were collected in zip lock sterile bags and labelled appropriately according to their market of purchase. The yellow garri labelled A1 as the first and the white garri labelled A2 as the second sample followed respectively C1, C2, B1, B2, D1, D2, E1, and E2 before conveying to the laboratory for Analysis.

Proximate Analysis of Garri

Composition of Moisture Content

The crucibles were washed and placed in the hot air oven to dry for 50°C for 30 minutes. The dried crucible was weighed and marked M1. 2g of each sample was added into each labelled crucibles weighed separately and marked M2. These crucibles were then heated in an oven under the temperature of 100°C for 2 hours, and allowed to cool down and weighed again

marked M3. The samples moisture was determined as the average weight difference (Ahn et al., 2014). Using the equation AOAC (Horwitz & Latimer, 2017).

$$\text{Moisture content (\%)} = \frac{M2 - M3}{M2 - M1} \times 100$$

Functional Properties of Garri

Swelling Content: The swelling capacity of the samples is obtained using the methods describe by (Sanni et al., 2008) In this procedure 5 grams of each garri samples was placed in a clean measuring cylinder and followed by the addition 25milliters of distilled water into the samples. The measuring cylinder was closed tightly, and the content was mixed thoroughly by inverting the cylinder for 2 minutes. After this it was inverted again and left to stand for 3 additional minutes, after which the final volume of the distilled water was measured to estimate the swelling capacity of the garri.

$$\text{Swelling capacity (\%)} = \frac{\text{volume of the garri in water}}{\text{Initial volume of garri}} \times 100$$

Microbial Sample Analysis

Microbial analysis was carried out by weighing 2g of each sample, suspended in peptone water and crushed by sterile mortar and pestle. After crushing, 4-fold serial dilutions technique was done by measuring 1g each employed in a well labelled test tube and added 9ml of sterile distilled water. Then 1ml of the stock solution was dispensed into another 9ml of distilled water. This was done up to 4th time, and this will be repeated for the ten samples (Orji et al., 2016).

Serial dilution

This technique was used to reduce microbial load in a sample. The stock solution is prepared by weighing 1gram of the samples, then turning it into a sterile test tube adding 9 milliter of distilled water into the test tubes. Then 1milliter of the stock solution is employed into the nest dilution series and the process is done continually until the last (Akoma et al., 2019; P. Thomas et al., 2015).

Cultivation of Sample

The serial dilution was used for inoculation; it was inoculated using streaking method were exactly 1ml aliquot from 10⁻⁴ dilution was aseptically inoculated into MacConkey agar and nutrient agar of each 1ml dilution for a total variable bacterial count. The inoculated plate was incubated at 35⁰C for 24 hours. At the end of the incubation period discrete colonies were enumerated and expressed as log of colony forming units (CFU) of diluted sample was calculated using the following formula (Clarence et al., 2009).

$$\text{Number of organism (CFU/g)} = \frac{\text{Number of colony} \times \text{dilution factor}}{\text{Volume of dilution cultured}}$$

Isolation and Purification of bacterial isolates was done using methods previously described by (Cowan & Steel, 1994; Edward et al., 2012)

Results

The findings of this study shed light on the microbiological safety, proximate composition, and functional properties of garri obtained from various open markets. As garri is a staple food in many Nigerian households, its safety and quality are paramount to public health.

Table 1 shows the moisture content of garri. Moisture content is a determinant of food stability and shelf-life. The garri samples analysed had moisture contents ranging from 5.50% (C2) to 9.00% (E1). High moisture levels, particularly above 8%, as seen in samples 9.00% (E1), are associated with increased susceptibility to microbial spoilage and while the lowest moisture content level is 5.50% (C2).

Table 2 shows the colony forming unit (CFU) of bacteria. Microbial Contamination and Load, the microbiological analysis indicated bacteria counts ranging from 1.42×10^3 CFU/g (B1) to 7.1×10^5 CFU/g (B2). These values surpass acceptable limits for ready-to-eat foods ($10^3 - 10^4$ CFU/g), particularly in samples 7.1×10^5 CFU/g (B2) and 6.4×10^5 (C1) that have the highest bacterial count. While 1.42×10^3 (B1) and 1.55×10^3 (E2) have the lowest bacterial count. The presence of high bacterial loads suggests inadequate hygiene during processing, handling, or packaging.

Table 3 shows a total of 10 bacterial contaminates *Escherichia coli*, was identified in 2(20%) samples, Market-Specific Observations Each market showed a unique profile of bacterial isolates: Agbor-Obi Market: *Escherichia coli* and *Enterobacter sp.*; Balake Market: *Staphylococcus albus* and *Citrobacter sp.*; Owa Market: *Klebsiella sp.* and *Staphylococcus aureus*; Ebu-Owa Market: *Proteus sp.* and *Enterococci sp.*; Alihagu Market: *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Escherichia coli*.

Staphylococcus aureus, which was isolated in 2(20%) samples, detecting wide spread of direct bare hands contact, contamination can by droplet sneezing or coughing from the handlers or processor. Other isolates include *Klebsiella sp*, *Enterobacter sp*, *Staphylococcus albus*, *Citrobacter sp*, *Proteus sp*, and *Enterococci sp*, from the garri sample accounting for (60%).

Figure 1 shows the mean Swelling Capacity of garri. Swelling capacity reflects the ability of garri granules to absorb water and expand, influencing its acceptability among consumers. Market variation suggests differences in cassava variety, fermentation duration, and granule structure. The mean swelling capacity ranges from 3.00% (EOM) to 3.60% (AOM).

Table 1: Proximate Analysis of Garri Samples from Various Markets

Market	Garri colour	Parameter	%M.C
Agbor-obi market	YG	A1	7.50
	WG	A2	8.50
Balake market	YG	B1	7.00
	WG	B2	8.00
Owa market	YG	C1	6.50
	WG	C2	5.50
Ebu-Owa market	YG	D1	8.50
	WG	D2	7.00
Alihagu market	YG	E1	9.00
	WG	E2	8.00

Key: MC: Moisture content, YG: Yellow garri, WG: White garri.

Table 2: Total Heterotrophic bacterial Counts of Garri Samples from Various Markets Colony forming Unit (CFU)

Market	Garri colour	Parameter	(10 ³ CFU/g)
Agbor-Obi market	YG	A1	84.93×10 ³
	WG	A2	42.46×10 ³
Balake market	YG	B1	1.42×10 ³
	WG	B2	7.1×10 ⁵
Owa market	YG	C1	6.4×10 ⁵
	WG	C2	65.75×10 ³
Ebu-Owa market	YG	D1	42.5×10 ³
	WG	D2	42.5×10 ³
Alihagu market	YG	E1	99.1×10 ³
	WG	E2	1.55×10 ³

Table 3: Bacterial isolated from garri samples in different locality

Sampling site	Yellow garri	White garri
AOM	<i>Escherichia coli</i>	<i>Enterobacter sp</i>
BM	<i>Staphylococcus albus</i>	<i>Citrobacter sp</i>
OWM	<i>Klebsiella sp</i>	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>
EOM	<i>Proteus sp</i>	<i>Enterococci sp</i>
AO	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	<i>Escherichia coli</i>

Key: AOM: Agbor-Obi Market, BM: Balake Market, OWM: Owa Market, EOM: Ebu-Owa Market, AO: Alihagu Market

Figure 1: Bar Chart Showing Swelling Capacity of Garri samples

Figure 1: Bar Chart Showing Swelling Capacity of Garri samples **Key:** AOM: Agbor-Obi Market, BM: Balake Market, OWM: Owa Market, EOM: Ebu-Owa Market, AM: Alihagu Market.

Discussion

The proximate analyses of moisture content in garri samples shows the quality and safety variability in the market. This study observed range of 5.50% to 9.00% which is of concern because, its moves from an acceptable level for good shelf life to a range that influences risk of spoilage. The moisture content of sample E1 9.00% is specifically of concern. Moisture levels above 8% compromise the storage stability of garri, particularly in humid tropical climates where microbial activity is naturally increased. With a level of moisture content creates an environment favourable for the growth of moulds, yeasts, and bacteria, including pathogenic species, leading to rapid deterioration, production of mycotoxin and reducing shelf life of the garri (Aguoru et al., 2014; Amadi & Adebola, 2008). The producers from Alihagu market E1 (yellow garri) shows the less dehydration during the frying process, or the product was improperly handled during post processing, allowing it to absorb atmospheric moisture during storage, cooling or in the open market. While the lowest moisture content sample C2 (white garri) 5.50% (Owa market) shows a well processed product with a high ability of long shelf life. This finding is consistent with (Okolo & Makanjuola, 2021) reporting very low moisture content is the key preventing microbial deterioration over months. In this study, the lowest moisture range of garri samples will make it less prone to microbial spoilage and contamination. The observed differences in the level of moisture content can be characterized based on the changes in temperature, rate of frying, packaging and the storage condition of final product (Kehinde & Udoro, 2013).

The swelling capacity of garri influences its desirability and nutritional value, as higher swelling capacity is linked to better texture and water absorption. The mean swelling capacity of garri samples from different markets ranged from 3.00% to 3.60%. The swelling capacity shows the ability of garri to absorb water by increasing the volume of the garri particles (Oduro et al., 2000). The variation in swelling capacity among samples could reflect differences in processing methods and cassava variety. This study shows that the garri was perfectly processed, which the producer fried the garri at high temperature successfully gelatinizing the starch. The quality of garri swelling capacity is 50% is a significant increase to the nutritional composition (Bamidele et al., 2014).

Microbial Contamination and Load, the microbiological analysis indicated bacteria load ranging from 1.42×10^3 CFU/g (B1) to 7.1×10^5 CFU/g (B2). The presence of high microbial load exceeds the required count ($10^3 - 10^4$ CFU/g), particularly in samples 7.1×10^5 CFU/g (B2) and 6.4×10^5 (C1) that have the highest bacterial count. The acceptable bacteria load for

(9.5×10^3 CFU/g – 6.7×10^4 CFU/g) were within the tolerable limits of 10^4 to 10^5 recommended by International Commission on Microbiological Specifications for Foods (Okolo & Makanjuola, 2021). The presence of high bacterial loads suggests inadequate hygiene during processing, handling, or packaging. The presence of *Escherichia coli* shows contamination from faecal matter, environmental exposure, or poor personal hygiene among handlers. Some of these bacteria are pathogenic and most are non-pathogenic but can cause opportunistic infections in immunocompromised individuals (Bennett & Mondy, 2003; Rufai & Wartu, 2023; Viana et al., 2025) .

The common practice of tasting garri with bare hands before purchasing further heightens the risk of microbial exposure. The occurrence of toxin-producing *Staphylococcus aureus* in samples from Owa market and Alihagu market underscores the risk of foodborne illness associated with improperly handled garri. *Staphylococcus aureus* a commensal of human microbiota can contaminate food process and handled with bare hands as such their presence in the garri samples suggest possible contamination from direct contact or aerial droplet which include sneezing or coughing by the garri producers, and handlers or retailers. (Omonigbo & Ikenebomeh, 2002; Bennett & Mondy, 2003; Okolo & Makanjuola, 2021;). *Staphylococcus aureus*, and *Enterobacter sp.* have also been added in food infections and intoxication causing diarrheal diseases among other complications particularly infant children, elderly and immunocompromised individual (Pal, 2022) . *Enterococcus sp.* as good bacteria which can serve as probiotics to boost the microflora of the gut among other useful benefits associated with probiotics, their presence is good for the health of the consumers of garri (Ajayi & Ajenifuja, 2025). These findings suggest localized issues of contamination possibly due to environmental sanitation, market design, and vendor practices.

Conclusion:

The analysis reveals that several garri samples sold in open markets do not meet microbiological safety standards due to high moisture content and significant microbial contamination. The detection of pathogenic bacteria indicates potential health risks, particularly when garri is consumed without further cooking. Market environments and post-production handling practices significantly influence product safety and quality. Considering the fact that garri is a staple food consumed by large population in the Ika locality, Nigeria at large and even other tropical African countries, it is important that these regions are encouraged to reduce the consumption of garri without thermal treatment to prevent food infections or food intoxications. The garri processors and retailers should be able adhere to strict personal hygiene and food safety awareness by using clean covered transparent

containers for sales to reduce direct and indirect contaminations by airborne droplets and spores of the isolates in dust and air.

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